

FRACTURE MECHANICS STUDY ON REHABILITATION OF DAMAGED INFRASTRUCTURES BY USING COMPOSITE WRAPS

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ABSTRACT

Infrastructures might be damaged by earthquake, fatigue, overload or sever environmental attacks in service. Many older bridges, buildings and other infrastructures are in need of seismic strengthening and rehabilitation. Effect of external reinforcement to damaged beam with composite wrap is analyzed in the present paper based on Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. Reduction of stress intensity factor at a crack tip, average membrane stress of the wrap, energy release rate of debonding between the composite wrap and beam are calculated, and the results are summarized in the normalized closed-form equations. Applicability of composite materials to structural rehabilitation is discussed from the theoretical results.

INTRODUCTION

Infrastructure might be damaged by fatigue, overload, fire, earthquake and sever or long term environmental attacks. Rehabilitation of the infrastructure is an urgent matter in civilized countries. Because of high rigidity, light weight and easy fabrication, fiber composites are considered to be well applied to the rehabilitation of the infrastructure. Saadatmanesh et. al [1-4] have demonstrated and reviewed excellent performance of composite materials applied to repair of concrete structural members. Reliability and durability as well as resistance to environmental attacks must be investigated in order to verify the applicability of composite materials to the rehabilitation

Our recent concern is how structural performance of damaged member is improved by external reinforcement with composite wrap. In the present paper, rehabilitation of an edge-cracked beam, as schematically shown in Fig. 1, is analyzed based on Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics.

MODEL DESCRIPTION

A single edge notched beam subjected to pure bending moment, M , is rehabilitated by wrapping composite strip on the cracked surface. The schematic figure is illustrated in Fig. 1. The beam with rectangular cross section with height, W , and width, B , has an edge crack with length of a . Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio of the base material are E and ν , respectively. The composite wrap with Young's modulus, E_R , has the same width of B but the thickness of t . It is assumed that through-the-width debonding area with length $2c$, extends both directions between the adhesive interface symmetrically with respect to the crack plane.

A two-dimensional mechanical model is proposed in Figure. 2. The debonded composite wrap is represented as a spring with compliance λ_d .

Figure 1 Cracked beam member rehabilitated with composite wrap

Figure 2 A model analyzed in the present study

Figure 3 Single edge notch specimen subject to bending moment and wedge opening force

$$\frac{\delta}{F} \equiv \lambda_d = \frac{2c}{E_R B t} \tag{1}$$

λ_d is a function of the debonding length, $2c$, and decreases with debonding area extends. Stress intensity factor, K_I , after rehabilitation with wrap bonded can be obtained as superposition of the stress intensity factor, K_{IP} , due to closure force, $-P$, and the applied stress intensity factor, K_{IM} , under pure bending, M .

$$K_I = K_{IM} + K_{IP} \tag{2}$$

Stress intensity factor, K_{IM} , of single edge notched beam under pure bending moment (see Fig. 3) has been obtained as Eqns. (3) and (4) [5,6].

$$K_{IM} = \frac{6M\sqrt{a}}{BW^2} F_M(\alpha) , \quad \alpha = \frac{a}{W} \tag{3}$$

$$F_M(\alpha) = 1.99 - 2.47\alpha + 12.97\alpha^2 - 23.17\alpha^3 + 24.80\alpha^4 \tag{4}$$

$$0 \leq \alpha \leq 0.6$$

Stress intensity factor, K_{IP} , due to wedge opening force as shown in Fig. 3 might depend on the location of the loading point and be a function of a/W and c/W , but Srawley and Gross [7] have suggested that the effect of c/W can be neglected if c/W and a/W are greater than or equal to 0.6 and 0.4, respectively. K_{IP} is obtained in Eqns. (5) and (6) under the conditions.

$$K_{IP} = \frac{P\sqrt{a}}{BW} F_P(\alpha) \tag{5}$$

$$F_P = \frac{2 + \alpha}{(1 - \alpha)^{3/2}} \{3.975 - 9.240\alpha + 16.219\alpha^2 - 15.477\alpha^3 + 5.817\alpha^4\} \tag{6}$$

$$0 \leq \alpha \leq 0.8$$

FRACTURE MECHANICS ANALYSIS

DEFORMATION

Consider the deformation of single-edge-notched beam subjected to pure bending moment, M , and wedge opening force, P , as shown in Fig. 3. We define the two states of the beam specimen, that is, uncracked and cracked members, and the deflection angle and the displacement at the loading points are expressed as the sum of the components with no crack and the increment due to existence of the crack.

$$\theta_{total} = \theta + \theta_{no\ crack} \tag{7}$$

$$\delta_{total} = \delta + \delta_{no\ crack} \tag{8}$$

Subscript of 'total' and 'no crack' indicate the amount of cracked and uncracked specimens, respectively. Variables, θ and δ , without subscript indicate the increments introduced by the crack. There are linear relations between the increments and the applied load for a given crack length.

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \theta \\ \delta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{MM} & \lambda_{MP} \\ \lambda_{PM} & \lambda_{PP} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M \\ P \end{Bmatrix} \tag{9}$$

Compliance λ_{ij} can be obtained by the following equations based on Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics [8,9];

$$\lambda_{MM} = \int_0^a \frac{2B}{E'} \left(\frac{K_{IM}}{M} \right)^2 da \tag{10}$$

$$\lambda_{PP} = \int_0^a \frac{2B}{E'} \left(\frac{K_{IP}}{P} \right)^2 da \tag{11}$$

$$\lambda_{MP} = \lambda_{PM} = \int_0^a \frac{2B}{E'} \left(\frac{K_{IM}}{M} \right) \left(\frac{K_{IP}}{P} \right) da \tag{12}$$

where E' is the equivalent Young's modulus of the base material and defined by Eqn. (13).

$$E' = \begin{cases} E & \text{for plane stress} \\ \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} & \text{for plane strain} \end{cases} \tag{13}$$

Substituting Eqns. (3) - (6) into Eqns. (10) - (12), we can obtain the compliance, λ_{ij} , as the polynomial function of the crack depth ratio, α .

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \lambda_{MM} &= \frac{72}{E' BW^2} \phi_{MM}(\alpha) = \frac{72}{E' BW^2} \frac{\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)^2} h_{MM}(\alpha) \\ \lambda_{PP} &= \frac{2}{E' B} \phi_{PP}(\alpha) = \frac{2}{E' B} \frac{\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)^2} h_{PP}(\alpha) \\ \lambda_{MP} = \lambda_{PM} &= \frac{12}{E' BW} \phi_{MP}(\alpha) = \frac{12}{E' BW} \frac{\alpha^2}{(1-\alpha)^2} h_{MP}(\alpha) \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{14}$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} h_{MM}(\alpha) &= 1.968 - 6.101\alpha + 10.215\alpha^2 - 6.995\alpha^3 \\ h_{PP}(\alpha) &= 30.601 - 63.063\alpha + 67.970\alpha^2 - 28.500\alpha^3 \\ h_{MP}(\alpha) &= 7.652 - 19.037\alpha + 25.611\alpha^2 - 14.539\alpha^3 \end{aligned} \right\} \tag{15}$$

Numerical integration and the least square method for curve fitting are adopted in the present study. in order to obtain the closed-form expressions.

$\delta_{no\ crack}$ is estimated based on the elementary beam theory by assuming that the wedge opening force is considered as the combination of the bending moment, $PW/2$, and the axial force, P .

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_{no\ crack} &= \lambda_{0MP} M + \lambda_{0PP} P \tag{16} \\ \lambda_{0MP} &= \frac{12c}{EBW^2}, \quad \lambda_{0PP} = \frac{8c}{EBW} \end{aligned}$$

The δ_{total} agrees with the extension of the spring, and the wedge opening force, P , which has the opposite direction and sign of F in Eqn. (1), must satisfy the condition.

$$P = -\frac{\lambda_{0MP} + \lambda_{MP}}{\lambda_d + \lambda_{0PP} + \lambda_{PP}} M \quad (17)$$

P is negative in the present model because a spring produces a crack closure force.

STRESS INTENSITY FACTOR, K_I , WITH WRAP BONDED

Substituting Eqn. (17) into Eqn. (5), we can estimate the effect of the closure force on the stress intensity factor, K_{IP} . The actual stress intensity factor, K_I , is the sum of the stress intensity factors, K_{IM} and K_{IP} , of the applied moment and closure force, respectively, as defined in Eqn. (2), the effect of the rehabilitation on the stress intensity factor, K_I/K_{IM} is obtained.

$$\frac{K_I}{K_{IM}} = 1 - R_1(\alpha, \beta) - \gamma \cdot R_2(\alpha, \beta) \quad (18)$$

β and γ represent nondimensional parameters of debonding length and wrap thickness, respectively, and defined by Eqn. (19).

$$\beta = \frac{E'}{E_R} \cdot \frac{c}{t}, \quad \gamma = \frac{E_R'}{E} \cdot \frac{t}{W} \quad (19)$$

E_R' is an equivalent Young's modulus of the composite wrap and defined by Eqn. (20).

$$E_R' = \frac{E_R}{1 + 4 \frac{E_R}{E} \cdot \frac{t}{W}} \quad (20)$$

Parameter, γ , has the value between 0.0 and 0.25 for any combination of t , W , E and E_R . Nondimensional functions, $R_1(\alpha, \beta)$ and $R_2(\alpha, \beta)$, in Eqn. (18) is calculated.

$$R_1(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{F_p(\alpha) \phi_{MP}(\alpha)}{F_M \{\beta + \phi_{PP}(\alpha)\}} \quad (21)$$

$$R_2(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{F_p(\alpha) \cdot \beta}{F_M(\alpha) \{\beta + \phi_{PP}(\alpha)\}} \quad (22)$$

In the case of very thin wrap, $\gamma \rightarrow 0$ and $\beta \rightarrow (E'/E_R)(c/t)$, the third term of Eqn. (18) can be neglected and the reduction of stress intensity factor by rehabilitation can be simply estimated by the first factor, $R_1(\alpha, \beta)$. The second factor, $R_2(\alpha, \beta)$, represents the additional effect of stiffness increase by composite wrap bonded.

AVERAGE MEMBRANE STRESS, σ_R , OF BONDED WRAP

Average membrane stress, σ_R , of debonded wrap and nominal bending stress, σ_0 , of uncracked beam are defined as follows;

$$\sigma_R = -\frac{P}{Bt}, \quad \sigma_0 = \frac{6M}{BW^2} \quad (23)$$

Normalized average membrane stress, σ_R , of wrap in the debonded region is calculated by Eqns. (24) - (26).

$$\frac{l \cdot \sigma_R}{W \cdot \sigma_0} = T_1(\alpha, \beta) + \gamma \cdot T_2(\alpha, \beta) \quad (24)$$

$$T_1(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\Phi_{MP}(\alpha)}{\beta + \Phi_{PP}(\alpha)} \quad (25)$$

$$T_2(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\beta}{\beta + \Phi_{PP}(\alpha)} \quad (26)$$

ENERGY RELEASE RATE, G_d , OF DEBONDING

Consider the deformation of the specimen subject to the bending moment, M , under the condition that crack length, a , and debonding area, $C = 2Bc$, are fixed. Because of linear elastic response, the complimentary energy, U_{total} , of the specimen is given by Eqn. (27).

$$U_{total} = U + U_{no\ crack} \quad (27)$$

$$U = \frac{1}{2} M \cdot \theta, \quad U_{no\ crack} = \frac{1}{2} M \cdot \theta_{no\ crack}$$

Energy release rate, G_d , of debonding is defined as the rate of complimentary energy, dU_{total}/dC , but the component, $dU_{no\ crack}/dC$, might be disregarded. It is assumed in the present study that G_d can be well estimated by dU/dC , that is, under the fixed bending moment,

$$G_d = \frac{1}{2B} \frac{dU}{dc} = \frac{M}{4B} \frac{d\theta}{dc} \quad (28)$$

From Eqns. (9) and (17), relation between θ and M are given by Eqn. (29)

$$\theta = \left\{ \lambda_{MM} + \frac{\lambda_{MP}(\lambda_{OMP} + \lambda_{MP})}{\lambda_d + \lambda_{OPP} + \lambda_{PP}} \right\} M \quad (29)$$

Substitute Eqn. (29) into Eqn. (28), we obtain nondimensional energy release rate.

$$\frac{\sqrt{2E_R t G_d}}{W \sigma_0} = Q_1(\alpha, \beta) \cdot Q_2(\alpha, \gamma) \quad (30)$$

$$Q_1(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\Phi_{MP}(\alpha)}{\beta + \Phi_{PP}(\alpha)} \quad (31)$$

$$Q_2(\alpha, \gamma) = \sqrt{1 - \gamma \cdot \frac{\Phi_{PP}(\alpha)}{\Phi_{MP}(\alpha)}} \quad (32)$$

RESULTS

Effect of rehabilitation on stress intensity factor given by Eqn. (18) is illustrated in Figs. 4 (a) and (b). $1-R_1(\alpha, \beta)$ and $R_2(\alpha, \beta)$ give primary and secondary effects on K_I/K_{IM} , respectively. The first term monotonically increase and asymptotically reaches to 1.0 as normalized debonding length, β , increases. The rehabilitation works more effectively to the specimen with larger crack depth ratio, $\alpha = a/W$.

Normalized membrane stress of the composite wrap is shown in Figs. 5 (a) and (b), which give functions of normalized debonding length with different crack depth ratio. The primary factor, $T_1(\alpha, \beta)$, decreases with debonding growth. In the case of thick wrap, the term of $T_2(\alpha, \beta)$ is not negligible and the membrane stress becomes higher.

(a) Primary factor, $1 - R_1(\alpha, \beta)$, of normalized K_I

(b) Secondary factor, $R_2(\alpha, \beta)$, of normalized K_I

Figure 4 Results of normalized stress intensity factor, K_I , at crack tip

(a) Primary factor, $T_1(\alpha, \beta)$, of normalized σ_R

Figure 5 Results of normalized membrane stress of composite wrap (continue to next page)

(b) Secondary factor, $T_2(\alpha, \beta)$, of normalized σ_R

Figure 5 Results of normalized membrane stress of composite wrap

(a) Primary factor, $Q_1(\alpha, \beta)$, of square root of normalized G_d

(a) Secondary factor, $Q_2(\alpha, \gamma)$, of square root of normalized G_d

Figure 6 Normalized energy release rate of debonding

Normalized square root of energy release rate is illustrated in Fig. 6 (a) and (b). The primary factor, $Q_1(\alpha, \beta)$, coincides with $T_1(\alpha, \beta)$, and decreases with debonding growth. The secondary term, $Q_1(\alpha, \gamma)$, is shown as a function of normalized wrap thickness, γ .

DISCUSSION

Consider the case that wrap thickness is much smaller than the height of beam, then we can assume that γ is small and the secondary terms in Eqns. (18), (24) and (30) are negligible. Under the condition satisfied, the normalized energy release rate of debonding coincides with average membrane stress. When it is assumed that debonding propagates under the criterion of $G_d = G_c$ (constant), average membrane stress also keeps constant value during debonding. This result means that fracture mode transition seldom occurs between debonding and wrap breakage.

Ratio, K_I/K_{IM} , is constant before debonding initiates. During debonding growth, a criterion, $G_d = G_c$ (constant), is assumed to be satisfied, and a relation between K_I and K_{IM} is obtained.

$$K_I = K_{IM} - \frac{F_p(\alpha)\sqrt{2E_R t a G_c}}{W} \quad (33)$$

This equation means that K_I is no longer proportional to K_{IM} during debonding but that the difference between them is kept constant. Strengthening of cracked beam primarily depends on the combined mechanical property, $E_R G_c$, that is, product of Young's modulus of wrap and fracture toughness of debonding. Design parameter, ta/W^2 , might be chosen in order to satisfy the required reduction of the stress intensity factor for given crack length.

CONCLUSIONS

Rehabilitation of cracked beam by using composite wrap is investigated. A model is proposed based on Linear Elastic Fracture Mechanics. Deformation, stress intensity factor at crack tip, average membrane stress of wrap and energy release rate of debonding are obtained from the theoretical consideration. The failure and fracture of rehabilitated beam are controlled by three nondimensional parameters, that is, the crack depth ratio, the nondimensional debonding length and wrap thickness which are defined in the present study. Applicability of composite wrap to rehabilitation of infrastructure is discussed based on the theoretical results. It is shown that the mechanical performance of wrap materials can be measured by $E_R G_c$, the product of Young's modulus of the wrap and the fracture toughness of debonding.

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